

Chichen Itza LEGO Concept Model

The purpose of this proposal is to present a concept design for a LEGO Architecture World Heritage model of Chichen Itza for consideration by the LEGO Architecture Design Team.

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Background

The LEGO Group is a Danish private company engaged in the production of a series of educational toys, which are sets of parts for assembling and modeling various construction objects (The LEGO Group, n.d.-a). One example is the LEGO Architecture series, a specialized product line that brings iconic architectural landmarks to life using LEGO bricks. This theme is aimed mainly at older children, teens, and adult fans of LEGO, emphasizing realism, creativity, and educational value. Sets in this line are designed to be display models rather than playsets, focusing on detailed, miniature recreations of famous buildings and cityscapes. They are also designed and built by a famous architect Adam Tucker, releasing the first architecture sets in 2008. Over the years, the LEGO Architecture series has featured well-known structures such as the Empire State Building, the Eiffel Tower, and the Burj Khalifa. One of its most popular branches is the "Skylines" subtheme, which combines multiple landmarks from a single city into one continuous base model, creating a visually compelling and informative scene (The LEGO Group, n.d.-a).

From 2016 to 2022, the LEGO Architecture Skyline series released a total of 14 sets, each highlighting iconic buildings from major cities around the world. These models feature a total of 13 unique cities. The geographic distribution of these sets shows a clear pattern: 4 sets represent cities from Europe, 5 from North America, 1 from Australia, 3 from South and East Asia, and 1 from the Middle East. While the selection covers a broad range of global locations, there are noticeable gaps in representation. No sets currently represent cities from Africa or South America, despite these regions being home to numerous culturally and architecturally significant sites (Brickset, n.d.). One example of the "Skylines" series is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: LEGO London from “Skylines” series (source: Brickset, n.d.).

By expanding into World Heritage Sites, LEGO has the opportunity to fill this gap and engage with a wider audience. World Heritage is the designation for places on Earth that are of outstanding universal value to humanity and as such, have been inscribed on the World Heritage List to be protected for future generations to appreciate and enjoy (UNESCO, n.d.-b). These include ancient cities, natural wonders, and architectural achievements. Incorporating these sites into the LEGO Architecture series would diversify the product line and contribute to educational goals aligned with the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities (United Nations, n.d.).

One site that stands out for its historical, architectural, and cultural value is Chichen Itza, located in the Yucatan Peninsula in Mexico. Recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1988,

Chichen Itza was one of the major cities of the Maya civilization and features some of the most iconic examples of Mesoamerican architecture (UNESCO, n.d.-a). In 2007, Chichen Itza was also recognized as one of the “New Seven Wonders of the World” by the New7Wonders Foundation (New7Wonders Foundation, n.d.). It was a center for politics, religion, and military power in pre-Columbian times and continues to be a symbol of indigenous Mexican heritage. Today, Chichen Itza is one of the most visited archaeological sites in Latin America and is internationally recognized as a cultural treasure.

Figure 2a: El Castillo, the most iconic structure on the site (source: Wikipedia, 2025).

Figure 2b: The Temple of Warriors (source: Chichen Itza, n.d.-b).

Figure 2c: El Caracol, or the Observatory (source: Chichen Itza, n.d.-c).

Chichen Itza's most iconic structures, such as El Castillo, the Temple of the Warriors, and El Caracol, make it ideal for a LEGO World Heritage model (Chichen Itza, n.d.-a). See Figures 2a, 2b, 2c. Each of these substructures is distinct in form and scale, allowing for variety within the limited brick count of 450 to 750 pieces. The site's geometric layout and strong architectural lines present unique design opportunities for creative LEGO interpretation.

Creating a LEGO model of Chichen Itza would serve both the clients and consumers. For The LEGO Group, this project offers a chance to expand its product line with a culturally rich and visually striking set that aligns with its mission to "inspire and develop the builders of tomorrow" (The LEGO Group, n.d.-b). For consumers, especially those interested in history and architecture, it provides a fun and meaningful way to engage with one of the world's most extraordinary archaeological wonders. The model could also be used in educational settings to teach about ancient civilizations, engineering, and Mesoamerican history.

By designing a Chichen Itza concept set, this project aims to celebrate global cultural heritage in a way that is both interactive and accessible, using LEGO bricks as a medium to tell the story of

a civilization that once thrived in the Americas and left behind one of the most breathtaking legacies in human history.

Design Requirements

This project aims to design a LEGO Architecture concept model of Chichen Itza, Mexico, which is a UNESCO World Heritage Site known for its stone-carved temples and historical significance. The goal is to create a digital prototype using Bricklink Studio that follows the expectations and standards of the LEGO Architecture skyline subtheme.

The main product of this project will be a digital LEGO model representing Chichen Itza, designed within a piece count of 450 to 750 elements, which is typical for skyline sets. The model will consist of several sub-models, each representing a distinct feature of Chichen Itza, such as El Castillo, the Temple of the Warriors, El Caracol. These sub-models will be connected on a single baseplate in a skyline layout.

The primary client for this project is The LEGO Group, which has shown increasing interest in promoting global sustainability and cultural education through its products. The secondary client is the LEGO Architecture Design Team, which is responsible for ensuring each model aligns with the brand's design principles, including realism, creativity, stability, durability, and educational value (The LEGO Group, n.d.-a).

To meet the design requirements, the model must adhere to the following criteria:

1) Brick availability

Only LEGO elements that are currently in production (2024-2025 years) and available in Bricklink Studio may be used. No custom or discontinued parts are allowed.

2) Functional design

The model must be stable, durable, safe, and easy to assemble, especially since it will be designed for adult fans and collectors. It must also look clean and polished for display purposes (The LEGO Group, n.d.-a).

3) Educational and aesthetic appeal

The design should reflect key architectural and historical elements of Chichen Itza while remaining visually balanced and engaging. The model should convey the cultural importance of the site through thoughtful arrangement and detail.

4) Brand embodiment

The design must align with the LEGO Group’s mission “to inspire and develop the builders of tomorrow,” spirit “only the best is good enough,” and core brand values: imagination, creativity, fun, learning, care, and quality (The LEGO Group, n.d.-b).

5) Cultural and global significance

The model should fulfill the goals of the World Heritage subtheme by encouraging the appreciation and preservation of Chichen Itza as a site of “outstanding universal value” (UNESCO, n.d.).

Concepts Considered

In developing the concept for a LEGO World Heritage model of Chichen Itza, two existing LEGO designs created by fans that focus on El Castillo were explored. These models provided insights into how builders have previously represented Chichen Itza architecture using LEGO elements. I analyze their limitations and explain how my model improves upon them by incorporating broader aspects of the Chichen Itza archaeological complex, aligning more effectively with the LEGO Group's Request for Proposal (RFP) for the World Heritage subtheme.

Model 1: LEGO Ideas: El Castillo Concept

This fan-submitted LEGO Ideas project captures El Castillo in a standalone form. It was submitted to the LEGO Ideas design contest on February 15, 2024 by SJbricks29265. The model replicates the pyramid's stepped structure, including the central staircases. The creator makes strong use of symmetry and layered plates to represent the pyramid's distinct form. Around the model I can see trees with grass representing the real natural environment around the pyramid (SJbricks29265, 2024). See the brick model in Figure 3.

Figure 3: El Castillo model from LEGO Ideas (source: SJbricks29265, 2024).

Limitations:

1) Absence of additional sites:

While this model is highly detailed, it includes only El Castillo and fails to reflect the broader cultural and architectural diversity of the Chichen Itza site, such as the Observatory or the Temple of the Warriors.

2) Piece count:

Even though the exact piece count is unknown, the model likely exceeds the 750-piece upper limit for LEGO World Heritage models, making it unsuitable for the LEGO Architecture subtheme.

3) Scale:

Dimensions of the model: height : 28,8 cm/11,3 in, length : 78,4 cm/30,9 in, width : 80,5 cm/31,7 in(SJbricks29265, 2024). These dimensions also exceed the typical dimensions used in the LEGO Skyline theme.

4) Composition:

The model is composed of a stand-alone display piece rather than a build made of smaller parts that fit together in a skyline, which makes it harder to adapt and less consistent with other sets in the LEGO Architecture series.

Model 2: Bricklink Studio: El Castillo Concept

This Bricklink Studio model offers a simplified and compact version of El Castillo, using sloped bricks to simulate the pyramid's steps. The pyramid is mounted on a baseplate with green elements and one tree. It was published on January 9, 2019 by Titanite_Chunk (Titanite_Chunk, 2025). See the model in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Simplified Bricklink model of El Castillo (source: Titanite_Chunk, 2025).

Limitations:

1) Lack of details:

This version of El Castillo is more compact and under the piece limit. However, it loses many iconic architectural features, such as the additional four staircases or the Chacmool statue at the top.

2) Simple palette:

The model relies heavily on uniform gray and beige tones, lacking the dynamic coloration that defines many LEGO Architecture skyline sets. While the light brown area near one of the stairs seems intentional, the actual heritage site does not have any similar details.

3) Absence of additional sites:

Like the previous model, it does not show El Castillo among the other major monuments of Chichen Itza, missing an opportunity to show the site's cultural and spatial complexity.

4) Piece count:

The piece count is 406, which is an insufficient count for LEGO World Heritage models (Titanite_Chunk, 2025).

Improvements in My Concept Model

My concept design addresses these limitations by capturing Chichen Itza as a whole, not just El Castillo. This concept design allows the model to better represent the rich cultural history of the World Heritage site.

1) Multiple landmark sub-models

My design includes El Castillo, the Temple of the Warriors, and El Caracol, or the Observatory. This diversity offers a richer narrative about Mayan innovation, astronomy, and social structure.

2) Skyline format

I adopted a horizontal skyline layout similar in style to LEGO's Paris or Tokyo sets, allowing me to present a compact but cohesive overview of Chichen Itza's main landmarks.

3) Visual storytelling

By varying scales, colors, and elevations, I reflect the ceremonial layout of the site and the relationship between its structures, creating visual interest and accuracy. For instance, El Caracol's circular shape contrasts with the stepped pyramids, signaling its role as an ancient observatory.

4) Design Efficiency

The model remains within the 450–750 piece constraint, using efficient tile stacking and color blocking to preserve architectural accuracy within the limited brick count.

5) Durability and display value

Each sub-model is built with stability and modularity in mind, making the final set visually appealing and structurally correct, in line with LEGO's brand values such as quality and learning (The LEGO Group, n.d.-b).

Together, these improvements make my concept a more complete and educational tribute to the heritage of Chichen Itza, fulfilling both the design requirements of the RFP and the mission of the LEGO Architecture World Heritage theme: to preserve and share the cultural richness of historical sites with future generations through imaginative, high-quality LEGO design.

Concept Selection

During the conceptual design phase of my Chichen Itza model, I developed and improved two key components: the upper temple structure of El Castillo and the stepped pyramid base.

An Upper Temple Block

Figure 5: Early prototype of an upper temple block.

This early-stage concept focused on the upper temple of El Castillo. See Figure 5. The model was built vertically with simple stacked bricks and extended plates to represent different layers and capture basic geometric proportions. However, it lacked an opening to represent the entrance

of the temple and did not feature an interior, which made it feel too plain and generic for a culturally significant structure like El Castillo.

Figure 6: Improved version of the upper temple with red Jaguar statue.

In the improved version, I added a front opening to better show the temple's entrance and give access to the ritual space. Inside, I added a small red bracket to represent the red Jaguar statue, a crucial figure in Mesoamerican ceremonial contexts, found inside this temple. In addition, the scale of the temple was slightly increased to improve visibility and draw more attention to this element. These changes made the temple not only more accurate but also more meaningful within the overall model. See Figure 6.

The Stepped Pyramid Base

Figure 7: Early prototype of the stairs.

In the first pyramid base design, I used a LEGO stair component to simulate the stepped structure. See Figure 7. In this model, the sloped stair element was embedded too deeply within the steps, making it nearly invisible from most angles. This design concept conflicted with the real El Castillo pyramid, where the stairways visibly project outward from the center of each face. The actual pyramid also had nine floors, compared to six in the initial design.

Figure 8: Improved version of the stairs.

In the improved version, I refined the model by increasing the number of floors to nine, accurately matching the structure of the actual pyramid. See Figure 8. I kept the same sloped stair element but adjusted its angle and placement to make the slope more outward-facing and visually distinct. This adjustment improved both realism and clarity, making the stair feature one of the main components of the model. Overall, these revised concepts better align with the design requirements of the LEGO Architecture RFP, such as realism, scale, and design choices that highlight the historical value of the site.

Concept Description

My concept model represents Chichen Itza, which is a UNESCO World Heritage Site located in the Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico (UNESCO, n.d.). The model was built using BrickLink Studio and consists of 746 LEGO pieces, following the scale and structure of LEGO's World Heritage site subtheme. It includes three distinct structures, such as El Castillo (Temple of Kukulcan) at the center, the Temple of the Warriors on the left, and El Caracol (the Observatory) on the right.

The purpose of this model is to showcase the architectural beauty of Chichen Itza and communicate its cultural significance in a way that is accessible to a global audience. By transforming ancient structures into a modern and educational LEGO format, this model seeks to promote awareness, appreciation, and preservation of one of the world's most historically rich and symbolically powerful archaeological sites.

Chichen Itza was a major center of the Maya civilization. It played an important role in politics, trade, religion, and in science, especially astronomy. The city's buildings were full of symbolism and were carefully designed to reflect the Maya people's beliefs about the universe, gods, societal hierarchy, and knowledge. Each of the three buildings chosen for this model shows a

different side of Maya culture. When placed together, they tell the bigger story of a civilization that deeply valued learning, spiritual life, and its connection to nature and the cosmos (Chichen Itza Blog, 2023a).

In the model, I used tan, light bluish gray, and dark bluish gray to represent stone materials and green to represent the natural surroundings of the original site. Additionally, there are some trees on the back side of the model since the actual site has some greenery. The entire model rests on the black-coloured base that is two plates thick, similar to the LEGO Architecture theme. See Figure 9.

Figure 9: The entire model of Chichen Itza in brick form.

El Castillo (Temple of Kukulkan)

Figure 10: Final version of El Castillo in brick form.

El Castillo, the central pyramid of Chichen Itza, is the most recognizable and symbolically rich structure of the site. See Figure 10. My LEGO model uses 341 parts in tan and light bluish gray to reflect the limestone materials of the original monument, while a polished tiled surface replicates the pyramid's refined stonework. Some bricks with masonry profiles were used to imitate the texture of the structure. The stepped pyramid form is constructed with stacked bricks and the stair element, and each of the four sides includes outward-facing staircases built with hinge elements. This design choice was because in the actual temple, the staircases are not only

architectural features but also play a vital role in the solar phenomenon that occurs during the equinox, when light and shadow create the illusion of a serpent descending the pyramid (Exploratorium, n.d.-a). By ensuring the stairways stand out clearly in my model, I emphasize this astronomical alignment, which was central to Maya cosmology (Chichen Itza Blog, 2023a). Inside, there is a main column to support the temple and eight smaller support structures for the stairs element.

At the top, I included a small temple chamber with a doorway. Inside, a red bracket represents the Jaguar Throne, a sacred figure in Maya ceremonial life representing power and connection to the spiritual world. While simplified in scale, this detail acknowledges the religious function of the upper temple, which housed offerings and symbolized the divine authority of the priestly elite (Rea, 2025).

The overall pyramid structure features nine floors, carefully matched in my model, to mirror the nine levels of the Maya underworld (Yucatan Tickets, 2025). By scaling the model to include this specific number, I connect the LEGO form to the cultural belief that El Castillo was not only a temple but also a cosmological map linking the heavens, earth, and underworld.

Thus, each design decision directly expresses the Maya's integration of architecture, astronomy, and religion. In LEGO form, the model demonstrates how the Maya embedded spiritual meaning into structural design, and it invites builders to engage with both the engineering and the symbolism of one of the world's greatest pyramids.

The Temple of the Warriors

Figure 11: Final version of the Temple of Warriors in brick form.

The Temple of the Warriors, positioned on the left side of the model, is built with 164 parts in tan, light bluish gray, and bright green, representing the limestone and surrounding vegetation of the actual site. See Figure 11. The stepped structure is constructed with stacked bricks, while a single central staircase is formed using hinge elements. This design choice emphasizes that, unlike El Castillo, which features four stairways, the Temple of the Warriors has one prominent staircase, symbolizing the focused ceremonial processions that took place there (Chichen Itza Blog, 2023b).

At the front, I used round bricks to recreate the columns of the Temple of the Thousand Columns, which in reality were carved with figures of warriors. By repeating these column shapes, the LEGO model conveys both the symbolic power of the space and its military character. These columns reflected Toltec influence on Maya design, and in LEGO form they highlight the blending of cultural traditions that defined the temple's architecture (Chichen Itza Blog, 2023a).

The upper section of the model includes a small enclosed chamber, representing the sacred area where rituals and sacrifices were performed. This choice connects directly to the temple's religious role, as historical evidence shows it was dedicated to the gods of war and sacrifice and used to ensure divine protection for the city through offerings (Chichen Itza 7, 2024). The use of tiles to smooth the surfaces reflects LEGO Architecture's polished aesthetic but also symbolizes the formality and importance of the site as a space of both spiritual and political authority.

These design elements express how the Temple of the Warriors embodied the Maya's fusion of military power, religious devotion, and Toltec-influenced artistry, making it one of the most complex and symbolically charged monuments of Chichen Itza.

El Caracol (The Observatory)

Figure 12: Final version of El Caracol in brick form.

El Caracol, located on the right side of the model, is built with 65 parts in tan, light and dark bluish gray, and bright green, representing both the stone material of the structure and the

surrounding vegetation. See Figure 12. To reflect the building's unusual form, I designed a half-domed tower resting on a raised platform, using curved and rounded bricks to capture its distinctive circular shape, which links to its function as an astronomical observatory (Exploratorium, n.d.-b). The elevated base of the model imitates the high stone platform of the real structure, which gave the Maya clear sightlines above the flat, forested Yucatan landscape (Exploratorium, n.d.-b).

El Caracol carefully aligns with the movement of Venus, a planet the Maya linked to war and religion, using its cycles to plan battles and ceremonies (Exploratorium, n.d.-b; Chichen Itza Blog, 2022). The building's windows were used to track the sun's solstices, equinoxes, and Venus's position (Chichen Itza Blog, 2022). Without telescopes, the Maya used these observations to guide farming, rituals, and leadership choices, showing their belief that the stars shaped daily life (Chichen Itza Blog, 2023a; Chichen Itza Blog, 2022).

Finally, I placed trees on one side of the model to represent the natural environment surrounding the observatory. This contrast between the built structure and greenery reflects the Maya's ability to integrate their sacred architecture into the broader landscape while still maintaining a direct connection to the cosmos (Chichen Itza Blog, 2023a).

Preserving the Story of Chichen Itza

These models contribute to the preservation of Chichen Itza by turning a historically complex site into an educational and creative experience. In LEGO form, these ancient structures become accessible to students, builders, and tourists around the world. This brick form of the site tells the story of a civilization that combined science, religion, and politics in one city.

Case For Continuation

My concept model of Chichen Itza meets all the necessary requirements described in the LEGO Architecture World Heritage Request for Proposal (RFP). It follows the guidelines for piece count, part selection, visuals, scale, and design values, while also expressing the brand's mission and identity.

Here are the criteria to which my model adheres:

1) Piece count

The model contains 746 LEGO elements, which is within the required range of 450–750 pieces. This allows for enough parts to show the important details of the site while keeping the build practical for production.

2) Brick availability

All pieces and colors used are currently in production by the LEGO Group as of 2024-2025. I confirmed this by checking each element in the Bricklink Studio program and comparing them with the Bricklink website's current part listings. This ensures that the model can be produced without creating new parts or using discontinued ones.

3) Aesthetic appeal and style

The design fits the LEGO Architecture style because it is a miniature display model that fits the Skyline subtheme. The landmarks are scaled to look balanced together, and the base is two black plates thick, which is a common standard for this theme. Small details like the trees behind the buildings help connect the model visually to the real Chichen Itza site.

4) Functional design

The model also shows the instrumental brand values of stability, durability, ease of use, and safety. Using Bricklink Studio, I ran a stability simulation that showed that most connections are legal and secure. The only exception was a hinge element, which the program flagged as unstable. See Figure 13. However, Bricklink Studio sometimes has limitations when checking hinges because these parts are adjustable. In this case, the same type of hinge was marked as more secure in other parts of the model, and in real life, the connection would work because friction and tension hold the pieces firmly in place. The sub-models are strong enough for safe handling, and the building steps can be explained clearly in instructions. Since only official LEGO elements are used, the model meets LEGO's safety standards.

Figure 13: The stability test from BrickLink Studio.

5) Brand embodiment

In addition, the model expresses the LEGO Group's brand identity and values. It supports creativity by using some pieces for different purposes than their usual, which adds unique design solutions. For example, the plant stem element is usually used as a stem for flowers or carrots,

while I used it to represent the entire tree. It supports learning by teaching builders about Chichen Itza's history, culture, and architecture. For example, building El Castillo shows its connection to astronomy, the Temple of the Warriors shows its ceremonial and political role, and El Caracol shows how the Maya studied the movements of the stars and planets. This reflects LEGO's mission "to inspire and develop the builders of tomorrow" and the spirit of "only the best is good enough."

6) Cultural and global significance

Finally, the model meets the main goal of the LEGO World Heritage subtheme "to foster appreciation and support for sites of profound natural and cultural value that are worth preserving for future generations." By turning Chichen Itza into a high-quality and accessible LEGO set, this design helps preserve and share the story of the Maya civilization with future generations.

For these reasons, I believe my model should move forward to the detail design stage. I would like to thank the LEGO Group and the LEGO Architecture Design Team for reviewing my proposal and for supporting the celebration of World Heritage sites through LEGO products.

References

1. Brickset. (n.d.). *LEGO Skylines*. Brickset. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from <https://brickset.com/sets/subtheme-Skylines>
2. Chichen Itza. (n.d.-a). *Chichen Itza ruins*. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from <https://www.chichenitza.com/ruins>
3. Chichen Itza. (n.d.-b). *Temple of the warriors*. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from <https://www.chichenitza.com/temple-of-the-warriors>
4. Chichen Itza. (n.d.-c). *El Caracol*. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from <https://www.chichenitza.com/el-caracol>
5. Chichen Itza 7. (2024, September 28). *Temple of the warriors*. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from <https://chichenitza7.com/temple-of-the-warriors/>
6. Chichen Itza Blog. (2022, September 9). *Why is El Caracol a masterpiece of astronomy?* Retrieved August 3, 2025, from <https://www.chichenitza.com/blog/why-is-el-caracol-a-masterpiece-of-astronomy>
7. Chichen Itza Blog. (2023a, July 20). *The cultural significance of Chichen Itza: An insight into Mayan civilization*. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from <https://www.chichenitza.com/blog/the-cultural-significance-of-chichen-itza-an-insight-into-mayan-civilization>
8. Chichen Itza Blog. (2023b, July 10). *The architectural brilliance of Chichen Itza: Exploring the Temple of Warriors*. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from <https://www.chichenitza.com/blog/the-architectural-brilliance-of-chichen-itza-exploring-the-temple-of-warriors>

9. Exploratorium. (n.d.-a). *El Castillo, Chichen Itza*. Ancient Observatories. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from
 - a. <https://annex.exploratorium.edu/ancientobs/chichen/HTML/castillo.html>
10. Exploratorium. (n.d.-b). *El Caracol, Chichen Itza*. Ancient Observatories. Retrieved August 3, 2025, from
 - a. <https://annex.exploratorium.edu/ancientobs/chichen/HTML/caracol.html>
11. New7Wonders Foundation. (n.d.). *Pyramid at Chichen Itza, Yucatán Peninsula, Mexico*. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from
<https://world.new7wonders.com/wonders/pyramid-at-chichen-itza-before-800-a-d-yucatan-peninsula-mexico/>
12. Rea, S. (2025, May 2). *El trono del Jaguar Rojo, el tesoro oculto dentro del Castillo de Kukulcán*. *Architectural Digest México y Latinoamérica*. Retrieved August 21, 2025, from
<https://www.admagazine.com/articulos/el-trono-del-jaguar-rojo-el-tesoro-oculto-dentro-del-castillo-de-kukulcan>
13. SJbricks29265. (2024, February 15). *Chichen Itza* [LEGO Ideas project]. *LEGO Ideas*. Retrieved July 22, 2025, from
<https://beta.ideas.lego.com/product-ideas/df7e1f6d-86ea-440f-a0fc-06a85790c232>
14. The LEGO Group. (n.d.-a). *Architecture*. LEGO. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from
<https://www.lego.com/en-us/themes/architecture>
15. The LEGO Group. (n.d.-b). *The LEGO brand*. LEGO. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from
<https://www.lego.com/en-us/aboutus/lego-group/the-lego-brand>

16. Titanite_Chunk. (2025, March 30). *Chichen Itza microscale* [BrickLink Studio model]. *BrickLink*. Retrieved July 22, 2025, from <https://www.bricklink.com/v3/studio/design.page?idModel=71011>
17. United Nations. (n.d.). *Sustainable cities and human settlements*. United Nations. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from
 - a. <https://sdgs.un.org/topics/sustainable-cities-and-human-settlements>
18. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (n.d.-a). *Archaeological site of Chichen Itza*. UNESCO World Heritage Centre. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/483>
19. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (n.d.-b). *What is meant by "World Heritage"?* UNESCO World Heritage Centre. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/faq/19>
20. Wikipedia. (2025, June 30). *Chichen Itza*. Wikipedia. Retrieved July 14, 2025, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chichen_Itza
21. Yucatan Tickets. (2025). *Chichen Itza: The ultimate guide to Mexico's ancient wonder*. Retrieved August 21, 2025, from <https://www.yucatanickets.com/chichen-itza-guide.html>